

Prevalence and Antimicrobial Susceptibility of *Klebsiella* Species in Clinical Specimens of Indoor and Outdoor Patients at a Tertiary Care Hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Klebsiella* spp. are Gram-negative, non-motile, capsulated rods that function as opportunistic pathogens responsible for a broad spectrum of nosocomial infections, including urinary tract infections (UTIs) and respiratory tract infections. The escalating prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains and Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL)-producing isolates constitutes a critical global public health challenge, particularly in developing nations such as Pakistan.

Objective: To determine the prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of *Klebsiella* species isolated from clinical specimens of indoor and outdoor patients at a tertiary care hospital in Rawalpindi, Pakistan.

Methods: A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted over three months at the Microbiology Laboratory, Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi. A total of 143 consecutive non-probability clinical isolates of *Klebsiella* spp. were obtained from various specimen types. Identification was confirmed by Gram staining and standard biochemical tests. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar, interpreted according to Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines.

Results: *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the predominant isolate. Urine was the most frequent specimen source (44.1%), followed by pus (18.2%) and wound swabs (16.8%). Female patients (55.2%) showed higher prevalence than males (44.8%); inpatients contributed more isolates (62.2%) than outpatients (37.8%). Highest resistance was recorded against amoxicillin-clavulanate (98%), cefotaxime (97%) and cefixime (96.7%). Colistin demonstrated the greatest efficacy (96.6% susceptibility), followed by gentamicin (82%), amikacin (78.1%) and tigecycline (75.5%).

Conclusion: *K. pneumoniae* isolates at this tertiary care centre exhibit alarmingly high resistance to commonly prescribed beta-lactam antibiotics. Colistin and aminoglycosides remain the most active agents. Continuous antimicrobial surveillance and stringent antibiotic stewardship policies are urgently required.

Keywords: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*; antimicrobial susceptibility; antibiotic resistance; ESBL; multidrug resistance; nosocomial infections; Pakistan

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1. INTRODUCTION

Klebsiella spp. are Gram-negative, non-motile, usually capsulated rods belonging to the tribe Klebsiellae within the family Enterobacteriaceae. The genus is named after German microbiologist Edwin Klebs (19th century). Among the six ESKAPE pathogens (*Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter* spp.), *Klebsiella* is the most frequently encountered organism in clinical settings [1]. The gastrointestinal tract, human nasopharynx, and external environment can be colonised asymptotically, and rising colonisation rates in hospitalised patients correlate with up to a sevenfold increased risk of abdominal infection [2].

Klebsiella is an opportunistic pathogen capable of causing a wide range of community-acquired and hospital-acquired infections — including urinary tract infections (UTIs), respiratory tract infections, and wound and soft tissue infections [3]. In recent years it has emerged as one of the world's leading causes of nosocomial infections, with increasing mortality particularly among immunocompromised individuals, neonates and the elderly; it is also increasingly implicated in severe community-acquired conditions such as pneumonia and meningitis [4].

On their cell surfaces, *Klebsiella* members normally express two distinct antigens: a capsular polysaccharide (K antigen) and a lipopolysaccharide (O antigen), both of which contribute to pathogenicity [5]. The thick capsular material prevents phagocytosis by polymorphonuclear granulocytes and inhibits killing by bactericidal serum factors, most likely through interference with complement component C3b activation [6–10].

K. pneumoniae has emerged as a predominant cause of hospital-acquired UTIs and bloodstream infections (BSIs), where antibiotic-resistant strains are increasingly difficult to manage and carry a significantly elevated mortality rate [12,13]. ESBL-producing *K. pneumoniae* strains acquire resistance through plasmid-mediated horizontal gene transfer, conferring broad cross-resistance across multiple antibiotic classes [21,22]. The subsequent evolution of carbapenem-resistant strains presents an alarming therapeutic challenge, as carbapenems represent the last reliable line of defence against MDR *Klebsiella* infections [23–30].

Pakistan, in common with other developing nations, bears a substantial burden of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in clinical settings. Published region-specific data from tertiary care hospitals in Rawalpindi remain scarce, yet such surveillance is essential for guiding empirical therapy. The present study was therefore conducted to determine the prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of *Klebsiella* species isolated from clinical specimens at Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Design, Setting and Duration

A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted over a period of three months following institutional approval of the research proposal. The study was carried out in the Microbiology Laboratory of Holy

Family Hospital — a major tertiary care hospital in Rawalpindi, Pakistan. All clinical specimens processed in the laboratory during the study period were considered for inclusion.

2.2 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Consecutive non-probability sampling was employed. A total of 143 samples were included, calculated using the WHO sample size calculator. *Klebsiella* species isolated from all clinical specimens across all age groups were included. Microorganisms other than *Klebsiella* were excluded.

2.3 Specimen Collection and Primary Culture

Klebsiella species were isolated from clinical specimens obtained from both outpatient department (OPD) and admitted (indoor) patients. Specimens — including urine, pus, wound swabs, blood cultures, throat swabs, body fluid aspirates, catheter tips (endotracheal tube [ETT], central venous pressure [CVP] line, Foley's catheter) and bile — were inoculated on MacConkey agar, blood agar and CLED (Cystine Lactose Electrolyte Deficient) agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Mucoid, circular, lactose-fermenting colonies were selected for further processing.

2.4 Gram Staining

Slides were properly labelled and de-waxed on flame. A single drop of distilled water was placed on the slide and the colony to be examined was emulsified. Heat fixation was performed by passing the slide through a flame 2–3 times. The fixed smear was then subjected to standard Gram staining: (i) flooded with crystal violet for 1 minute; (ii) washed with a gentle indirect stream of tap water for 2 seconds; (iii) flooded with Gram's iodine (mordant) for 1 minute; (iv) decolourised for 15 seconds; (v) counterstained with safranin for 30–60 seconds; (vi) washed and blot-dried. Results were read under oil immersion by light microscopy. *Klebsiella* species appeared as Gram-negative, non-motile, rod-shaped organisms.

2.5 Biochemical Identification

The following biochemical tests were performed for confirmation of *Klebsiella* species:

Catalase Test: Positive — vigorous bubble formation was observed on emulsification of colonies in hydrogen peroxide.

Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) Agar: Both slant and butt turned yellow (acidic), indicating fermentation of glucose, sucrose and/or lactose. Gas production (CO₂ and H₂) was evidenced by agar displacement.

Sulphate Indole Motility (SIM) Test: Negative for most *Klebsiella* species; positive indole reaction was observed for *K. oxytoca*, indicating tryptophanase activity.

Citrate Utilization Test: Positive — *Klebsiella* metabolised citrate as its sole carbon source, producing an alkaline environment that shifted the bromothymol blue indicator from green to blue.

2.6 Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (AST)

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed on confirmed *Klebsiella* isolates by the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton (MH) agar, in accordance with Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) interpretive criteria. A 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard suspension was prepared and used to inoculate MH agar plates by sterile cotton swabbing. Antibiotic-impregnated disks were placed on the inoculated surface, pressed gently, and plates were incubated overnight at 37°C. The antibiotic diffused radially, producing a concentration gradient; a clear zone of inhibition formed where bacterial growth was suppressed. Zone diameters were measured in millimetres (mm) and compared against CLSI standard breakpoints.

The following antibiotic disks were evaluated: amoxicillin-clavulanate (30 µg), amikacin (30 µg), gentamicin (30 µg), ceftriaxone (30 µg), ceftazidime (30 µg), cefotaxime (30 µg), imipenem (10 µg), cefepime (30 µg), ciprofloxacin (5 µg), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole/cotrimoxazole (25 µg), piperacillin-tazobactam (110 µg), cefoperazone-sulbactam/sulzone (105 µg), tigecycline, colistin (10 µg), fosfomycin and nitrofurantoin (300 µg).

2.7 Statistical Analysis

All data were tabulated and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 25). Frequency and percentage were calculated for all categorical variables.

2.8 Ethical Consideration

Institutional consent was obtained from Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi, prior to commencement of research activities. Patient data were handled confidentially and anonymously throughout the study.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Distribution of Isolates by Specimen Source

Among 143 *K. pneumoniae* clinical isolates, urine specimens constituted the largest proportion (n=63, 44.1%), followed by pus cultures (n=26, 18.2%), wound cultures (n=24, 16.8%), catheter tip cultures (n=16, 11.2%), aspirates/body fluids (n=16, 11.2%), throat cultures (n=8, 5.6%), blood cultures (n=3, 2.1%) and bile (n=1, 0.7%) (Figure 1).

3.2 Prevalence by Gender and Patient Category

Of all 143 isolates, 64 (44.8%) were recovered from male patients and 79 (55.2%) from female patients, demonstrating a significantly higher prevalence among females. With respect to patient category, 89 isolates (62.2%) were obtained from inpatient (indoor) specimens compared to 54 isolates (37.8%) from outpatient specimens, indicating a substantially greater burden among admitted patients (Figure 2).

3.3 Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern

According to antibiogram results of all 143 *K. pneumoniae* isolates, the highest resistance was recorded against amoxicillin-clavulanate (98%), cefotaxime (97%) and cefixime (96.7%). Colistin demonstrated

the greatest efficacy, with 96.6% of isolates classified as susceptible. The complete antimicrobial susceptibility data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Antimicrobial Susceptibility Pattern of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Isolates (n=143)

Antibiotic	Susceptible (%)	Resistant (%)
Colistin	96.6	3.4
Gentamicin	82.0	18.0
Amikacin	78.1	21.9
Tigecycline	75.5	16.1
Sulzone (Cefoperazone-Sulbactam)	69.2	30.8
Tazocin (Piperacillin-Tazobactam)	63.2	36.8
Imipenem	56.0	44.0
Ciprofloxacin	21.0	79.0
Ceftriaxone	12.5	87.5
Ceftazidime	13.7	86.3
Cefepime	13.3	86.7
Cotrimoxazole (Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole)	11.0	89.0
Cefotaxime	3.0	97.0
Cefixime	3.3	96.7
Amoxicillin-Clavulanate (Augmentin)	2.0	98.0

AST = Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing; CLSI = Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute interpretive criteria applied throughout.

Among the 63 urine isolates specifically, 73.2% demonstrated resistance to nitrofurantoin and 61.5% to fosfomycin. In addition to colistin, susceptibility was observed to gentamicin (82%), amikacin (78.1%), tigecycline (75.5%), sulzone (69.2%), tazocin (63.2%) and imipenem (56%).

4. DISCUSSION

Klebsiella has emerged as a highly virulent nosocomial pathogen over recent decades. While historically recognised as a cause of community-acquired pneumonia, UTIs, bacteraemia and neonatal septicaemia, the emergence of hypervirulent forms with metastatic dissemination potential — primarily causing pyogenic liver abscess, meningitis and endophthalmitis — represents a new and alarming clinical paradigm [44]. An in-depth understanding of virulence factors and their mechanisms of immune evasion is essential for developing effective containment strategies.

In the present study, urine was the predominant specimen source (44.1%), consistent with the well-established role of *K. pneumoniae* as a leading aetiological agent of UTIs. This was followed by pus

cultures (18.2%), wound cultures (16.8%) and catheter-related specimens (11.2%), reflecting the pathogen's propensity for nosocomial transmission in invasive-device settings. These findings are concordant with a study conducted at two major hospitals in Hamadan, Iran, involving 83 *K. pneumoniae* isolates, which similarly reported cefotaxime as the most-resisted antibiotic (92%) with complete colistin susceptibility, and a higher prevalence among inpatients [45].

Comparable high-resistance patterns have been reported from Pakistan. At Bolan Medical Complex, Quetta, all isolates (100%) were resistant to amoxicillin, cefixime, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, cefotaxime and ceftriaxone, followed by ciprofloxacin (76.2%) and sulphamethoxazole (66.7%) [46]. Similarly, at Dhaka Medical University, Bangladesh, *K. pneumoniae* showed high resistance to sulphamethoxazole-trimethoprim (90.67%), ceftriaxone (90.67%), cefotaxime (89.33%) and ceftazidime (89.33%), with tigecycline identified as the most effective agent [47] — a pattern closely mirrored in the present study.

The higher prevalence among female patients (55.2% vs 44.8%) observed in the current study is consistent with a study from Duhok City, Iraq, involving 130 clinical isolates, where females accounted for 99 of 130 isolates [48]. This likely reflects the anatomical predisposition of females to UTIs, the most common source of *K. pneumoniae* in both studies.

Carbapenem resistance constitutes a particularly serious concern. An MDR *K. pneumoniae* isolated from an ICU patient at the Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences, Islamabad, was found susceptible only to tigecycline and colistin [49]. In the present study, imipenem susceptibility was 56%, indicating that nearly half of the isolates have already breached this critical antibiotic class. A Shanghai-based retrospective ICU study further corroborated these trends, reporting the highest resistance to amoxicillin-clavulanate (93.5%) and ciprofloxacin (92.3%), with relatively lower resistance to colistin (11.5%) and tigecycline (23%) [50].

The overall resistance profile observed in this study reflects a systemic pattern of AMR escalation attributable to multiple mechanisms, including ESBL production, AmpC beta-lactamase expression, altered outer membrane porin expression, efflux pump upregulation and horizontal gene transfer. The simultaneous resistance to fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin 79%) and cotrimoxazole (89%) further limits oral therapeutic options, particularly for outpatient management.

These findings collectively underscore the critical need for region-specific antimicrobial stewardship programmes, rational prescribing practices and routine surveillance of resistance patterns in tertiary care settings across Pakistan.

5. CONCLUSION

Klebsiella pneumoniae is the predominant species isolated from clinical specimens at this tertiary care hospital in Rawalpindi, with urine as the most common source. The isolates demonstrate alarmingly high resistance to beta-lactam antibiotics — particularly amoxicillin-clavulanate, cefotaxime and cefixime — attributable to beta-lactamase production. Colistin remains the most effective agent (96.6% susceptibility),

with additional activity demonstrated by gentamicin, amikacin, tigecycline, sulzone and tazocin. The prevalence is greater among female patients and admitted inpatients than among outpatients.

These results strongly indicate an urgent requirement for continuous antimicrobial surveillance and the implementation of a strict antimicrobial stewardship policy in healthcare settings across Pakistan. Without such intervention, the rising tide of MDR *K. pneumoniae* threatens to render existing empirical treatment protocols ineffective, with serious consequences for patient outcomes in both hospital and community settings.

DECLARATIONS

Author Contributions: Muhammad Rumais conceptualised the study, performed microbiological procedures, collected and analysed data, and drafted the manuscript. Izza Rashid contributed to data collection, laboratory work and critical review of the manuscript. Both authors approved the final version.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Data Availability: The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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